

Increasing Youth Engagement in a Global Warming Environment

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Abstract:

In a world where "unprecedented images" are rapidly changing, spiritual threats aimed at winning the heart and consciousness of the younger generation are increasingly dangerous in our social life, along with many positive processes. In this difficult situation, the most important thing for us remains the protection of children from harmful influences, as well as vigilance and vigilance.

Keywords: spirituality, man, spiritual purification, education of creative power, respect, honest purity, spiritual growth and life, life satisfaction, devotion to the ideas of independence, state youth policy.

In the development of civil society, there are many ways, ways and factors to increase the social activity of young people. In our opinion, the example of those who, realizing the essence of inspiration and spirituality, devoted their lives to improving the well-being and well-being of the people, is one of the most striking examples. Where there is life and man, there is also inspiration. Throughout his life, everyone encounters him knowing or not knowing. When we encounter this, we completely forget about existence and experience such pleasure that we easily find new things.

And then a person inspired by God will find such inner peace and joy that these feelings and circumstances will become his source. He equates inspiration with the content of life and finds peace, peace, joy and happiness. Not everyone was lucky enough to understand him, master all his secrets and subordinate their inspiration to him. Therefore, those who gain God's blessing and become his "rulers" will be fertile, blessed, clean, and rich in discovery. To mind [1].

Everyone was confident that the next independence day would be kind. "Peace flourishes with a just donation" (Amir Temur). Thousands of facts testify to this. Over the year, politics in Uzbekistan has changed. New systems of representative bodies of social economy, spirituality and education, state

power have been launched. All this is closely connected with the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who perfectly mastered the art of governing the country and the people carrying out creative work.

In all his closing speeches, the light of spirituality shines. Because "spirituality is a force that moves a person to spiritual cleansing, to the aging of the heart, strengthens the inner peace of a person, strengthens his will, strengthens his faith and strengthens his conscience." [2]".

Like everything that the sun radiates, the spirituality of independence gives creative strength to all our ideological, economic, educational actions, creates bright opportunities for an honest and fair life, achieving perfection. It fills our hearts with love, respect, honest purity, spiritual growth, and life satisfaction. These truths are the core of his inspiration. He is a leader who lights the hearts of people with the light of the spirituality of independence and directs them to prosperity, to humanity, to good. A wise leader who knows a comprehensive approach to any problem and shows how to make it fair. Wisdom is who finds and decides everything. This man, who still works tirelessly, never tired of creating, surprises us all, and many of us are powerless to work. Because the President inspires the people[3].

Only then will the number of perfect people increase, and as they increase, they will improve the lives of our people and Uzbekistan; will become the world's torch! If young men and women put the power of this model example into their hearts, their activity, trust, and loyalty are further strengthened, and virtue increases, and this leads to world influence, and therefore to perfection. He "announces greatness, wisdom based on knowledge, greatness, well-being [4].

In a world where "unprecedented images" are rapidly changing, spiritual threats aimed at winning the heart and consciousness of the younger generation are increasingly dangerous in our social life, along with many positive processes. In this difficult situation, the most important thing for us remains the protection of children from harmful influences, as well as vigilance and vigilance.

We will continue to resolutely continue our great work to educate young people in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, the ideas of independence, the realization of its talent and abilities, noble aspirations". In order to increase the activity of young people, a presidential decree "On measures for radical reform and bringing to a new level of state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" of June 30, 2020 and a resolution "On organizing the activities of the Agency for Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan" of June 30, 2020 were developed.

The main tasks and activities of the Agency are:

- development and implementation of a unified state policy, strategic directions and state programs in the field and directions related to youth;
- preparation of proposals for the improvement of regulatory legal acts aimed at supporting young people in the country, protecting their legal rights and interests;
- state control over compliance with legislation in the field of youth policy;
- education of young people in the spirit of devotion to the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, education of the younger generation[5].

It can be said without exaggeration that today our entire country, including the Agency, is young people with potential, capable of thinking and tirelessly working on themselves.

In a period of reform and change, young people get the opportunity to express themselves. But this opportunity - when it becomes a huge potential, an unsurpassed force - when our youth will act decisively, study hard, experience from the bottom of their hearts responsibility to the Motherland and its people and be worthy of it.

Today, out of 875 employees of the Agency system, 223 are young people (25.5 percent). 16 or 9 percent of them are women.

In total, 21 young people under the age of 30 work in leadership positions, in addition, our colleagues aged 30 to 40 work in almost all responsible positions in the Agency. Nevertheless, we want young people to work more on themselves in this direction, to show their abilities and abilities.

In the central office, 36 percent of our young employees (14 out of 39) speak 2 foreign languages, and 58 percent speak Russian.

in order to improve the experience of young employees in the Agency system, they are involved in permanent business trips, last year 9 employees were sent to advanced training and business trips to foreign countries;

25 employees participate in advanced training courses of the Academy of Public Administration, are sent to retraining and advanced training courses, soon the conditions for training more than 200 employees will be created at the Scientific Center for Corporate Governance, most of whom are our youth.

As a youth representative, the leader of the primary organization of the Youth Union is actively involved in all social events. Participation in all commissions established in the Agency system is ensured [6].

LITERATURE PUBLICATIONS:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. We are building our great future together with our courageous and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, NMIU, 2017
2. Journal of Educational Technology. № 2011/3
3. Kadyrov P. He will "reap... Tashkent, 1971, - B.107
4. Umurov H. Inspiration. - Tashkent: Navro'z, 2018. - B.64
5. Sh. Mirziyoyev. 30 June 2020 Decision No. PQ-4768